

THE NOTION OF SEMANTICS AND LEXICOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with exploring the branches of linguistics, namely semantics and lexicology. The prime aim of research implementing detailed information and full notions to these terms. On the top of that, the functions of semantics and lexicology, as well as the role of them are written in article.

Introduction

Lexicology is the science studying the lexis [also called the lexicon] of a language. It is usually conceived as the branch of linguistics concerned with the nature, meaning, history, and use of words and word elements. Very often it is also related to the critical description of lexicography. Lexicology in itself has to do with all particularities of words, that is, with morphology, syntax, word-formation, etymology, word-combination, meaning and history of a language. In this sense lexicology was first conceived as a branch of philology. Today it is increasingly treated as a branch of linguistics, associated with such terms as lexeme, lexical field, lexical item, lexicon, lexis, on the premises that these terms can offer a more precise and useful basis for the study of language than imprecise terms such as words and vocabulary [4.8p].

Lexicology ought to be described in phrases of simple tenets lexis (phrases or vocabulary) and that means, something to be described in itself. That is, lexicology these days is diagnosed with the examine of that

means in the phrases of a language. The hassle with lexicology therefore is to kingdom what the lexis of a language is, beneathneath what attitude it's miles to be studied, and what's the component you search for in its examine. Bearing those issues in thoughts you could say that the examine of that means (both in case you name it lexicology or in case you name it lexematics, as we're going to do) constitutes an area in itself, that is, an autonomous area. This manner that the examine of the phrases constituting the vocabulary of a language, the set of lexical gadgets of a language, has to cope with gadgets: phrases on the only hand, and that means on the other. These gadgets are complicated sufficient and consequently you need to outline them formerly in themselves earlier than you begin with the definition of lexicology. But those gadgets ought to be studied one at a time and of their personal phrases.

Words and meanings represent 2 objects simply identifiable. Speakers will easily establish words and meanings a minimum of intuitively. However, the study

of the knowledge of a language cannot begin with the first identification of those objects. It's necessary to look at initial bound assets given in reference to both.

Semantics On the other hand semantics is the science studying meaning in general. Semantics is usually related to the following four different disciplines: a) Semasiology, a branch of linguistics dealing with the study of the meanings of words and sentences: their denotation, connotation, implications, and ambiguities. The study of words and meanings can be made at the different levels constituting the analysis of language: phonological, grammatical (morphological and syntactic) and semantic. b) Philosophy, the study of logical expressions and the principles determining the truth or falsehood of sentences. c) Semiotics, the study of signs and what they refer to and the responses to those signs by speakers. d) General use. In general use, that is, in the intuitive study of meaning, semantics is of interest since the meanings of words include denotation, connotation, implications, and ambiguities. Semantics thus is a general discipline, not specific, of the lexis of a language. The science due to study the lexis of a language must be defined in its proper terms not giving for granted the definition of meanings and words [4,9p].

There are numerous branches of lexicology. The preferred observe of phrases and vocabulary, no matter the particular capabilities of any precise language, is called preferred lexicology. Linguistic phenomena and homes not unusual place to all languages are known as language universals. Special lexicology focuses on the outline of the peculiarities within side the vocabulary of a given language. A branch of observe referred to as contrastive lexicology gives a theoretical basis on which the vocabularies of various languages may be as compared and described,

the correlation among the vocabularies of or extra languages being the scientific priority.

Descriptive lexicology offers with the vocabulary of a language at a given stage of its evolution. It researches the capabilities of phrases and their unique shape as a function inherent within side the system. In the English language the above technology is orientated in the direction of the English phrase and its morphological and semantic systems, getting to know the interdependence among those aspects. These systems are recognized and outstanding through contrasting the character and association of their elements.

Within the framework of lexicology, both synchronic (Gr syn □together□, □with□ and chronos □time□) and diachronic or historical (Gr dia □through□) approaches to the language suggested by the Swiss philologist Ferdinand de Saussure (1857-1913) are effectively realized. Language is the reality of thought, and thought develops together with the development of a society, thus the language and its vocabulary should be studied in the light of social history. Every new phenomenon in a human society in general, which is of any importance for communication, finds a reflection in the corresponding vocabulary. A word is considered to be a generalized reflection of reality; therefore, it is impossible to understand its development if one is ignorant of the changes in socio-political or everyday life, manners and culture, science of a linguo-culture it serves to reflect. These extra-linguistic forces influencing the evolution of words are taken into the priority consideration in modern lexicology [7.3p].

Methodological review

The two approaches should not be contrasted, as they are interdependent since every linguistic structure and system actually exists in a state of constant development so that the synchronic state of a language system

is a result of a long process of linguistic evolution. As every word is a unity of semantic, phonetic and grammatical elements, the word is studied not only in lexicology, but in other branches of linguistics, too, lexicology being closely connected with general linguistics, the history of the language, phonetics, stylistics, and grammar. According to S. Ullmann, lexicology forms next to phonology, the second basic division of linguistic science (the third is syntax). Consequently, the interaction between vocabulary and grammar is evident in morphology and syntax. Grammar reflects the specific lexical meaning and the capacity of words to be combined in human actual speech. The lexical meaning of the word, in its turn, is frequently signaled by the grammatical context in which it occurs. Thus, morphological indicators help to differentiate the variant meanings of the word (e.g., plural forms that serve to create special lexical meaning: colors, customs, etc.; two kinds of pluralization: brother → brethren - brothers; cloth → cloths - clothes). There are numerous instances when the syntactic position of the word changes both its function and lexical meaning (e.g., an adjective and a noun element of the same group can change places: library school - school library).

Meaning is something particularly problematic. Meaning defines language: it is in direct connection with the very existence of language. At the same time meaning manifests itself in language. Language is nothing but the creation of meanings³. In this sense meaning is universal and necessary. But meaning is not abstract but real. Meaning manifests itself in the words and expressions of a language. [4.13p].

It manifests itself as diverse, that is, as a couple of meanings. In this feel which means is something belonging to specific languages, something historical. In the

primary feel, which means is the inner characteristic of language. It is not anything however contents of conscience, something created whilst language is created, that is, whilst language is spoken. In the 2nd feel, which means is something objective, belonging to a specific language and consequently something not unusualplace presented to audio system in a specific community. In this feel, which means is virtual. Meaning constitutes the number one characteristic of language, that is, to mean. Language is decided and consequently described through its significant characteristic, its inner willpower, the characteristic of developing meanings. In this feel, language is self-reliant because it has an inner willpower. Since language is real, something lived through audio system, which means seems in contexts and situations, that is, which means is feel as well. The number one characteristic of language should now no longer be burdened with the instrumentality of language, that is, with the use fabricated from language. Language is instrumental, that is, it's far used for precise functions the maximum vital of which is communication. The instrumentality of language cannot be overestimated. Language cannot be described within side the use fabricated from it. Language is to be described through its number one characteristic, its inner willpower. The use of language constitutes the outside willpower of it. Language cannot be described with its outside determinations however its inner willpower. Under the attention of its inner willpower language is self-reliant, as we have already said. Under the attention of its outside determinations language isn't always self-reliant however instrumental.

Types of meaning.

In the technique of speaking linguistic meaning is manifest in many ways: in the

technique of speaking the following kinds of meaning can be distinguished:

Lexical meaning

It is that the which means with reference to the essence of linguistic apprehension of the world. it's the solution to the question, what do you perceive? What does one apprehend? It consists within the legal instrument or primary systematization of expertise by suggests that of words of a language. it's the peculiar and explicit configuration of facts of expertise created by each language. the first organization of expertise by suggests that of words of a language may have different forms and should lean in numerous classes of the language. For example, the actual fact of expertise creating you say that «you feel cosy and therefore comfortable» is systematised with 2 words, heat and heat in English; equally the pairs young and youth mean the state of affairs having to do with the appliance getting on to completely different linguistics objects or with states of affairs denoting age; deep and depth alter states of affairs having to do with the extent of the bottom extending down from the surface; and high and height denote a state of affairs having to try to to with the position of things in connection with the human of these things. all told these pairs the state of affairs denoted is that the same: they represent a specific criterion introduced by the language so as to conceive the objects within the world. This criterion does not exist in itself: they represent helpful creations by the language in order to systemize things (=pragmatic affairs in my circumstance touching me) in the world. during this manner you'll describe things, and say The wall is high; The mountain is high however at an equivalent time you'll say The height of the wall; The height of the mountain, The state of affairs represented in each cases is the same. The which means of high is that the same

because the meaning of height however considered from completely different perspectives. Each of them describes an equivalent state of affairs.

Category meaning

It is that the quite which means with reference to the mode however the linguistic apprehension of real things is sent in a very language. it's the answer to the question, however does one apprehend things? it's the which means of grammatical classes (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs). during this method heat differs from warmth, though they need an equivalent lexical meaning. High and height; young, youth, old and to become older mean otherwise since, though they have an equivalent lexical which means, they convey reminder meaning having to try and do with the method the significance is conveyed. The content words same on top of denote different states of affairs. Adjectives apply the state of affairs they convey to the state of affairs denoted with the headword. Nouns denote one thing as constituting linguistics objects. And verbs refer the which means they convey to states of affairs with capability of building totally different relationships with the elements within the state of affairs involved. In this sense, The young members of the family differs from, The young in the family In the first case you refer some members belonging to the family who are young but in the second you refer members who are defined as young within the family. In the first case they are merely referred to as young; in the second one they are defined as young.

Instrumental meaning.

It is the kind of meaning relating to the contents conveyed by morphemes, either if they are independent or not. For example, the -s morpheme of some tables means plurality, but in Peter's house plays the function of determination, that is, it plays the function of a determiner. In he comes it means the third

person singular present simple. In the same way the determiner the in the man orientates a category of objects to a particular object so that the expression does not mean □the category of man□, that is, the category of human beings, but □a particular and determined member of the category of man□. Similarly, some in the expression some man orientates the category to an indefinite member of the class.

Syntactic or structural meaning.

It is the meaning conveyed by lexematic and catemematic words with morphemes within a sentence. It is the contribution of all elements making up a sentence and specifying a particular aspect of that sentence. In this sense expressions like 32 The English defeated the Picts, and 33 The Picts were defeated by the English. have the same designation and the same lexical and category meanings but they are to be dealt with different points of view. The first

example is to be analysed as {determined (Agent) + past + active (Patient)}; the second one as {determined (Patient) + past + passive (Agent)}. That is, the different meaning conveyed has to do with the combination of words, that is, with syntax. In this sense the meaning conveyed by the combination of the elements of the language belongs, not to words, but to the very combination of words. It belongs to the system of the language. Plurality, singular/plural, present/past/future, perfective/imperfective, comparison/non-comparison are types of meaning belonging to structural or syntactic meaning.

Conclusion

The research illustrates basically concerning these two notions, semantics and lexicology. Moreover, several subgroups of these linguistic branches are implemented. Till the today, majority of scientists, linguists have been getting research and investigations in order to open new manners in this field.

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